

Industrial Collaborations for Curriculum Reforms in Business Education in Rivers State Universities

Zems, Eunice Chidiebere & Nwineh, Letombari Princess (PhD)

Department of Business Education,
Rivers State University, Nigeria

Corresponding Authors' Email: nwineh.princess@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

Absence of relevant curriculum, results in skills mismatch between industrial requirement and actual skills possessed by business graduates and the end point is continued unemployment. Industries in Rivers State seem to be left out in curriculum planning. From 42 Lecturers, the study investigates collaborations between Business education programs and industries in Rivers State for curriculum reforms. Specifically, the existing curriculum gaps in Business Education curriculum that require industrial collaborations for improvement and strategies employed to ensure involvement of industries, are being probed. Instrument for data collection was a checklist and questionnaire titled "Industrial collaborations for curriculum reforms Questionnaire". Mean, simple percentage and standard deviation were used to answer two research questions. Findings revealed that there are gaps in business education curriculum which industrial collaborations could remedy and these include; gap in current industrial skill requirements, and technology usage. The study also found that very minimal strategies were employed to ensure industrial involvement in curriculum reforms. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there are existing gaps in Business Education curriculum and minimal strategies are employed to ensure the involvement of Industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs, other strategies like field trips, consultancy services and collaborative research are yet to be adequately employed. Among others, recommendations were made that Business Education curriculum planners in Rivers State should employ more strategies to ensure industrial involvement in curriculum reforms such as consultancies and collaborative research.

Keywords: Industrial, Collaborations, Curriculum Reforms, Business Education

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum has deep root and relevance in the academic circles but its bearing spreads far beyond the school walls to the economy, business operations, employability and self-worth of graduates. For this reason, various researchers have been attracted to the concept, interpreting from their different views, what curriculum really is and who should be involved in its design. Campbell-Philips (2020) described curriculum as a learning guide, governed by school, designed to facilitate learning and address student's educational need. Further explanations revealed that curriculum boosts the reputation of schools and attracts learners. This description is true, however it seems to be confining curriculum to school activities; facilitating learning and attracting learners, curriculum is far more crucial. Curriculum is the account of content to be studied, the organization, teaching, learning methods and arrangement for evaluation (Knight and Trowler, 2001). Curriculum exceeds evaluation. At the end of a planned content, teaching methods duly applied and evaluation, graduates would be rolled out, with the assumption that they are work ready. So curriculum is actually the road map to imparting relevant skills, knowledge and attitude for work and life. It is the blueprint of skill and knowledge to be infused into the workforce, clearly spelling the sequence of what would be taught per time and how it would be done. As such, curriculum reform should not be a pure academic endeavour, it requires the inputs of practitioners, particularly Business Education Curriculum, requires the input of individuals, currently playing on the business stage, in its curriculum reforms. Campbell-Philips (2020) echoed that Business Curriculum design should be influenced by the Industry.

Round the globe and over the years, businesses have experienced tremendous, endless changes, caused by the emergence of new technologies, innovative methods of production, marketing and office operations. Gill and Hu in Kee-Luen (2009) noted that Business discipline is dynamic and there is constant need for reassessment. The knowledge and skill requirement for business job roles 10 years ago, may not be exactly the same currently. So graduating prospective business employees with stale and less relevant skills could be an unintended outcome of the entire business academic process if Business Education programmes are not adequately collaborating with industries for curriculum reforms. Barnett (2011) elucidated the need for Institutions to keep their fingers on the pulse of industries not only to fill skill gaps but heighten competitiveness of their graduates in an educationally progressive world. This can only be achieved if Business Education programs maintains a strong bond with the industry.

From inception, Business Education as a field of study was coined from industry. Nino (2010) accounted that Business Education originated in the early part of the 20th century and was shaped by the forces of the market place; business education was not created based on research and scientific methods, but it evolved based on industry procedures and practices. Following trending industrial practices, Business Education produces skilled manpower for businesses. Nwafor (2014) explicated that Business Education is an aspect of learning that prepares individuals for roles in Business and offers them knowledge about business. For Business education graduates to successfully assume roles in business and gain required knowledge about business, its curriculum content should be in tandem with recent business environment requirements. Ugwuoke (2011) earlier maintained that Business education is a work focused, skill and technology based course. This statement imposes it that Business Education programmes must have its gaze on the field, to ensure that knowledge garnered by enrollees can be fruitfully applied on the field. The curriculum must be industry led following business tides and trends. This can only be possible if Institutions offering business education courses, have consolidated collaborations basically for curriculum reforms.

Ayonmike Igberadja, Igberaharha and Okeke (2015) saw collaboration as the relationship formed between two parties to exchange resources and expertise. So if business education collaborates with industries, relationships geared for exchange of resources and expertise could result. Aina and Akintunde (2013) beheld collaboration as a voluntary arrangement between two parties to execute a project with the aim of sharing profit and loss. Viewing from this lens, Business Education programs should voluntarily reach out to willing industries to update their curriculum. The reach out referred is different from meeting industries to attend events and make specific donations. A strong and sustained relationship enacted for understanding the navigation of trends and upcoming in the industry should exist. Documentation of favourable terms to curriculum development should be paramount from inception. Egbewole (2011) earlier viewed from this perspective and described collaboration as a contractual arrangement formed between two parties involving development and financing. In such collaborations, partners' resources are pooled and responsibilities divided so that efforts are complementary.

There are several mutual benefits from such relationships, among which are; The industries workforce demand, would be met. Research in recent times have loudened the lament over the mismatch of industrial skill requirements and actual skills possessed by graduates of business programs. Engelhart and Mupinga (2020) revealed that several efforts have been made to reduce the mismatch between employers' expectations and actual skills possessed by prospective employees. If these collaborations are in place, industrial skill requirements and skills being transmitted from the school would align better.

Business Education programs in Institutions, were these collaborations exist will benefit access to current industrial facilities for hands on experiential learning, thereby enriching the teaching learning process and current ideas from the place of experience is infused. Also imputes from the industries would be more easily reached. Mbah, Obi, Ehimen and Onyebuanyi (2018) further added that collaborations with industry will reduce the skill mismatch and align the skills infused in schools with the skills required in the industry, this was achievable if the school pays industrial visits and involves the industries in regular seminars and trainings. Ahmed, AbRahim and Abdullah (2015) earlier identifies, consultancy services, cooperative work study with industries and shared facilities as means by which institutions could extend hands of partnership to industries.

Theoretical framework

Resource Dependency Theory – Pfeffer and Salancik (2003)

The resource dependency theory by Pfeffer and Salancik (2003) provides explanatory value to this study and it holds the following assumptions;

- Organizations are connected to other entities within the environment
- None of these organizations can work autonomously
- Organizations depend on resources to survive
- Because resources are limited, organizations exchange resources and power structure are placed, shifting power to participants with most resources
- There are consequences of this process.

Relating the above theory to the current study, the institution where business education programs are done are educational organizations that do not stand to survive and remain relevant on their own, they connect to various other organizations, fundamentally to produce manpower for them. These institutions may not have the entire resources required, so there is the need for collaborations, in this case, the school blends in for curriculum reforms. The schools

may lack sufficient resources and timely knowledge of skill requirement which the partnering organization provides and in turn, the consequence is a ready work force, armed with needed skills to function in these organizations.

Statement of Problem

The problem of unemployment has not been particular to Nigeria, other countries seem to have same experience but what is worrisome is that business graduates have been found as a reasonable fraction of the unemployed. In Malaysia Kee-Luen (2009) studied the trend and found that 30% of the unemployed graduates in Malaysia were Business graduates. The general contention was that business graduates lacked the knowledge and skill required for employment, so institutions should work closely with professionals outside the school system for the development of relevant curriculum. Researchers from the United States seem to have similar findings. Cunningham and Villaseno (2016) illuminated that employers reported challenges in hiring employees who possess workplace readiness skills and blamed schools for not teaching the skills the labour market needs. This ugly trend has raised concern among parents and Business Educators. Engelhart and Mupinga (2020) identified collaboration as the remedy to skill deficiency in work place. Hence the need to find out what the case is in Nigeria, particularly, Rivers State; what are the existing gaps in Business education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement. Are there strategies employed to ensure the involvement of industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs. It is in the bid to provide empirical findings to these queries that this study is being carried out.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate collaborations between Business Education programs in Rivers State Universities and industries for curriculum reforms. The study will address two specific objectives which are to find out the following:

1. The existing gaps in Business education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement.
2. The strategies employed to ensure the involvement of industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What are the existing gaps in Business education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement?
2. What are the strategies employed to ensure the involvement of industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs?

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Rivers State. The population of the study comprised the 42 Business Education Lecturers in the two Rivers State owned Universities, 20 from Rivers State University and 22 from Igantius Ajuru University of Education. Sample size of 26 was derived using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for the study was a checklist and a questionnaire titled "Industrial Collaborations for Curriculum Reforms in Business Education (ICCFBE), Structured on the 4-point rating scale and checklist. Responses on sections 1 were on the checklist while section 2 were rated on a four point rating scale of 4 strongly Agree (SA), 3 Agree (A), 2 Disagree (D), and 1, Strongly Disagree with cut of mean of 2.50. The instrument was faced validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was determined through Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient method for measuring of internal consistency of the instrument. A total of 10 respondents who were not part of the sample were used in testing the reliability of this study. The reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained. 26 Copies of the instrument were administered and retrieved by the researcher at the spot. Percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are the existing gaps in Business education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement?

Table 1: Shows the Responses on the Existing Gaps in Business Education Curriculum that Require Industrial Collaboration for Improvement

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	YES	NO
	THE FOLLOWING GAPS EXISTS IN BUSINESS EDUCATION CURRICULUM		
1.	TECHNOLOGY USAGE GAPS IN BUSINESS EDUCATION CLASSES		
	Computers	40%	60%
	Projectors	70%	30%
	Phones	40%	60%
	Virtual Reality Application	98%	2%
	Smart Boards	100%	0%
	Internet	60%	40%
2.	Industrial Experience for Lecturers	70%	30%
3.	Industrial Experience for students like Field trips (Different from SIWES)	95%	5%
4.	CURRENT INDUSTRIAL SKILL REQUIREMENT		
	Big Data	100%	0%
	Human Machine Interface	100%	0%
	Cultural Intelligence	40%	60%
	Information Processing	55%	45%
	Proactive thinking	60%	40%
	Leadership	48%	52%
	Lifelong learning	60%	40%
	Multitask	49%	51%
	Collaborative thinking	40%	60%
	Problem solving	60%	40%
	Team work	40%	60%
	Metacognitive thinking	50%	50%
	Interpersonal skill	40%	60%
	Communication	30%	70%
	Self-Management	60%	40%
	Relationship Management	70%	30%

Source: Field survey, 2021

The results in Table 1 reveal the existing gaps in Business education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement. Technology usage gaps exist as 40% agrees to computer usage gap, 70% agree to projector usage gap, 40% agree to phone usage gap, 98% agree to virtual learning gap in curriculum, 100% affirms gap in Smart Board usage and 60% agrees to gap in Internet Usage. Industrial Experience for Lecturers was also an existing gap, Industrial Experience for students like Field trips (Different from SIWES) was also a gap and Current industrial skill requirement was also an existing gap as evident on the above table. 100% responses was that Big Data skills and human machine interface skills were not part of Business Education curriculum, cultural Intelligence, Information Processing, Proactive thinking, lifelong learning and multi task skills as a gap had, 40%, 55%, 48%, 60% and 49% yes responses respectively while collaborative thinking problem solving, Team work, Metacognitive thinking, Interpersonal, communication, Self-Management and relationship management were also agreed to as industrial skill requirements that were gaps in Business Education curriculum.

Research Question 2: What are the strategies employed to ensure the involvement of Industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs?

Table 2: Shows the Response of Business Education Lecturers on Strategies Employed to Enhance the Involvement of Industries in Curriculum Reforms in Business Education Programs

S/N	STATEMENT	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	MEAN	DECISION
1	Industrial Visits is a strategy employed in my department to strengthen relationships with the industry	0	13	13	0	2.5	Agree
2	We organize excursions and field trips to get industrial imputes for our curriculum	0	8	10	8	2	Disagree
3	We provide and receive consultancy services from industries to boost the contents of our courses	0	0	12	14	1.5	Disagree
4	Seminar and Workshops with resource persons from the industries are organized for updates on industrial happenings	0	0	13	13	1.5	Disagree
5	We are involved in Contract Research with industries	0	0	12	14	1.5	Disagree
6	We organize industrial Training Programs	12	11	3	0	3.4	Agree
7	We are involved in Collaborative Research with industries	0	0	20	6	1.8	Disagree
8	We exchange of Laboratories and other Facilities with industries	0	0	14	12	1.5	Disagree

Source: Field survey, 2021

As evident on table 2, industrial visits and industrial training programs on S/N 1 and 6 respectively have the mean responses above the criterion mean of 2.5 and are agreed upon as the strategies employed to ensure the involvement of Industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs. Other strategies like excursions and field trips, receiving and providing consultancy services, seminars with industrial resource persons, collaborative research and exchange of facilities had their mean below the criterion mean and are therefore not agreed upon as the strategies employed to ensure the involvement of Industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there are existing gaps in Business Education curriculum that require industrial collaboration for improvement; these gaps include; technology usage, Industrial Experience for Lecturers and students like field trips (different from SIWES) and Current Industrial skill requirement. Furthermore, it was concluded that minimal strategies like industrial visits and training programs are employed to ensure the involvement of Industries in curriculum reforms and development of Business Education programs, other strategies like field trips, consultancy services and collaborative research are yet to be adequately employed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. That Business Education curriculum planners in Rivers State should seek industrial involvement in curriculum reforms and development to ameliorate gaps in technology usage, industrials experiences for Lecturers and students and industrial skill requirement.
2. That Business Education Departments in Rivers State Universities should employ more strategies to ensure the involvement of industries in curriculum reforms and development, such as consultancy services and collaborative research with industries.

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